

ARE MIRACULOUS GIFTS STILL FOR TODAY?

By

Prasanna Kumar Monditoka M.Div., M.Pharm.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, I argue for classical cessationism and maintain that miraculous gifts (gifts of prophesy, speaking in tongues, and interpretation of tongues) ceased in the apostolic age. We are no longer expected to seek supernatural miraculous gifts in the present age. However, God the Holy Spirit is still working in the world to bring people to Christ, heal people as we trust and pray, and guide as we seek his counsel. My position is in line with the cessational view of Richard B. Gaffin and other classical cessationists with an exception in rationale. I maintain that there were two experiences of baptism in the early church and there were two different uses of the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit” in the New Testament.¹ In 1 Corinthians 12:13, Paul mentioned that—in one spirit we were all baptized—to denote the regenerative baptism of the Holy Spirit. However, in Acts 1:4-5, Luke used the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit” to refer to the supernatural empowerment of the Holy Spirit in the apostolic period.² The special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit did not continue after the period of the apostles as it served the purpose of affirming the witness of the apostles (Heb 2:24). Therefore, I infer that the supernatural miraculous gifts of the Spirit have ceased. In this paper, first, I would like to articulate my view with biblical and theological arguments and philosophical arguments. Then, I would like to clarify some misconceptions about cessationism.

¹ John Piper, “What is the Baptism of the Holy Spirit,” *Desiring God* (blog), September 14, 2021, <https://www.desiringgod.org/interviews/what-is-the-baptism-of-the-holy-spirit>.

² John Piper argued in his blog that there are two uses of the word “baptism of the Holy Spirit.” He maintained that the first use of the word in 1 Corinthians 12:13 refers to the receiving of the Spirit at conversion and the second use of the word in Acts 1:4-5 refers to the empowerment by the Spirit and it occurs multiple times in a -believer’s life. However, I maintain that the baptism of the Holy Spirit in Acts 1:4-5 refers to the unusual supernatural empowerment of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic period, therefore, I maintain that it will not continue.

Cessationism

Classical cessationism maintains that miraculous gifts (gifts of prophecy, speaking in tongues, and interpretation of tongues) were ceased in the apostolic age.

Distinctness

First, cessationism needs to be understood correctly. Cessationism maintains that God gives various gifts to the members of the church for the edification. However, when it comes to the spiritual gifts, we maintain that there are some supernatural unusual gifts in the apostolic period discontinued after the apostles. When we refer the word “miraculous,” we understand it as a highly unusual or less common. The miraculous gifts of prophesy, speaking in tongues, and gifts of healing were not usual, and they were ceased in the apostolic age. However, we still believe that God performs miracles of healing in some circumstances when we pray. However, this is different from the gift of healing and signs of apostles in apostolic age.³ We disagree with the views of Pentecostalism, Charismatics, and the third wave movement on the continuation of supernatural unusual gifts, signs, and miracles.

Inauguration of the New Covenant

Second, the miraculous gifts are associated with the inauguration of the new covenant and intended to witness the apostolic witness. The fresh and unprecedented arrival of the Holy Spirit resulted in the outburst of the new covenant age with the outpouring of the Spirit, the explosion of gifts, and a new empowerment of the disciples for the missions. This is the fulfillment of the prophesy of Joel 2:18-27, and it resulted in speaking in tongues in a powerful way. In Acts 1:4-8, the resurrected Jesus promised the disciples that they will be baptized with the Holy Spirit in the upcoming days. It is evident that here Jesus referred to an unusual

³ Richard B. Gaffin, *Are Miraculous Gifts for Today? 4 Views*, edited by Wayne A. Grudem (HarperCollins Christian Publishing, 1996), 41-42.

supernatural outpouring of the Holy Spirit on the disciples which empowers them to be witnesses in Jerusalem, and in all Judea and Samaria, and to the end of the earth.

Apostolic Witness

Third, God affirmed the work of the apostles as they witness the message of the gospel through signs and wonders (Acts 5:12-16, Ephesians 2:20, 2 Corinthians 12:12). Once the message of the apostles is affirmed and sealed, there is no need for the miraculous gifts. Although miraculous gifts continued in the church during the apostolic age, there is no indication of the normative principle for their continuation.

Biblical Canon

The miraculous gifts are not expected to continue after the biblical canon is closed. God has revealed himself fully through prophets, person of Jesus Christ, and apostles and affirmed the person, work, and mission of Jesus Christ (Hebrews 1:1-2). In Hebrews 2:4, the author mentions that "...God also bore witness by signs and wonders and various miracles and by gifts of the Holy Spirit distributed according to his will (ESV)." If the signs, miracles, and gifts are intended to witness the apostolic witness and their message and the canon is closed after the full disclosure within the apostolic age, it is safe to conclude that the unusual signs, wonders, and gifts are not expected to continue after the mission is accomplished. If we uphold the sufficiency of scriptures for rule of faith, conduct, and edification, we do not have to seek further miraculous gifts after canon is established for edification.

Supernatural Outpouring Baptism of the Holy Spirit in the Apostolic Age

Fourth, miraculous gifts were part of the supernatural outpouring baptism of the Holy Spirit in the apostolic age. If the supernatural outpouring baptism of the Holy Spirit fulfilled its

purpose and discontinued in the apostolic age, it follows that miraculous gifts were also discontinued. The special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit did not continue after the period of the apostles as it served the purpose of witnessing the message of the gospel proclaimed by the apostles (Heb 2:24). There are at least three or four special events in Acts (Acts 2:1-4, 8:14-17, 10, and 19:1-6). However, there is no mention of the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit in the epistles and apostles did not give a normative principle to the church. Although Paul mentions the baptism in the Spirit in 1 Corinthians 12:13 which does not refer to a special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit (as in the case of Acts 1:4-5), rather, it refers to the regenerating baptism of the Spirit.

In the epistles, Christians are encouraged to be filled by the Spirit (Eph 5:18) and empowered by the Spirit (Rom 15:13, Eph 3:16), however, the context does not suggest a special empowering baptism of the Spirit, rather, it suggests that believers should sing psalms and hymns and grow in their faith, love, and hope. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that the special empowering baptism of the Holy Spirit is not normative for all believers. Instead, we are born again by the regenerative baptism of the Spirit (1 Cor 12:13), and we should seek to be filled with the Spirit so that we give thanks and grow in love, faith, and hope (Rom 15:13, Eph 3:16).

Clarification on Misconceptions

Cessationism Does not Limit the Work of The Spirit

Pentecostals, Charismatics, and supporters of miraculous gifts in current age argue that cessationists put the Spirit in a box. They argue for the windiness of the Spirit (John 3:18) and they argue that we should not limit the work of the Spirit. However, John 3: 18 does not refer to disorderliness, rather, it refers to sovereign control of the Spirit. He is not limited by our

expectations. However, God the Spirit does not promote disorderliness and chaos in the church (1 Corinthians 14:33, 40).⁴

Cessationism Does not Promote Intellectualism at the Expense of Emotionalism

Some argue that cessationism promotes intellectualism and biblicism and they argue that it neglects genuine emotions and work of the Holy Spirit. They critique that cessationists have God the Father, Son, and the Bible in place of the Spirit. They argue that the overemphasis on the scriptures leads to the detachment from the guidance of the Spirit and his empowering work. However, this is not a legitimate critique. Although some churches fail to submit to the leading of the Spirit and lack of teaching orthopraxy and orthopathy due to lack of proper biblical exegesis, it does not suggest that cessationism discourages orthopraxy and orthopathy. On the other hand, the Spirit helps believers through the exposition of scriptures (John 6:63, 16:14).

⁴ Gaffin, *Are Miraculous Gifts for Today*, 25.